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Greenery method for Synthesis of some alkali and alkaline earth metallic nanoparticles and its antibacterial screening activity

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Abstract

In the presence study of science and technology has greater significance for the development of nanoparticles and its physicochemical properties. Alkali and alkaline earth metallic nanoparticle has synthesized by using various plant extract and metallic solution. However, biogenic reduction of metal precursors to produce corresponding metallic nanoparticle is eco-friendly, low cost, free of chemical contaminants for medical and biological applications. The synthesized Metallic nanoparticle is found to be more susceptible towards the bacterial strains.

Keywords: Tulsi; Turmeric; Bael and Castor leaf powder; Nano-particle; Bacterial activities

1. Introduction

Nano technology is an important field of modern research dealing with preparation, methods and manipulation of particle size ranging from 1 to 100nm, mention to as nanoparticles [1]. They are showing remarkable properties such as size and shape respectively[2]. However, Colours of nanoparticle also depends on the particle size and shape. Many researchers and scientists have shown great interest in their unique features and found that numerous nanoparticle materials revealed toxicity at the nanoscale size. To overcome the problem of toxicity, nanotechnology and green chemistry merge to fabricate nature-friendly nanoparticles via plants, microbes, etc[3]. Researchers have developed many synthetic routes for nanoparticle fabrication which wellness a notable benefit to nature & environment via clean, nontoxic, and environmentally adequate “green chemistry” methods which include organisms such as bacteria, fungi, plants[4].

For the study of Nano-particles following analysis had taken. These have FTIR, UV-VISIBLE, PSA, SEM & antimicrobial activity etc. These are fundamentals test analysis to the properties of Nano-particles[5-6]. Greenery synthesis of metallic nanoparticles materials properties has varied from materials prepared by other methods. Synthesized metallic nanoparticles may emphasize the reduced toxicity, stability and implacability; also it has enhanced the potential range of shapes, compositions and sizes of synthesis of metallic nanoparticles convert into a broad domain and new nanomaterials applications due to coating of capping agents[7].

Nano technology are wide range of applications like food packaging, in medicine (Especially in cancer treatment) agriculture and in waste water treatment etc. Green synthesis of metallic Nano-particles can be synthesized by various routs and one of the most important routs is a biological, in this rout we have been plane synthesizing nanoparticle from any body part of plant materials like roots, flowers, fruits, leaves etc.

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2. Material and methods

2.1. Materials

Potassium nitrate, Sodium nitrate, Calcium nitrate (Sigma–Aldrich, USA) and all other reagents used in this study were of analytical grade. In this experiment was used doubled distilled water.

2.2. Plant Leaf Extraction Procedure

Collect the leaves of Turmeric, Bael and Castor from the farm area of raver and Yawal tahasil areas and washing the leaves two or three times with distilled water. Drying the leaves under the clear sunlight for one week. This dry leaves is grinding by mixer and convert into powder. Taking 10 gm of leaf powder (Tulsi, Turmeric, Bael and Castor) in 250 ml beaker then adding 200 ml of distilled water. Dissolve it and making homogeneous solution. Heat the mixture on magnetic stirrer at 60-70°C for 5-7 hours. Cool the reaction mixture at room temperature & settled down precipitate for 2-3 days then forming the two layers in beaker then separate out upper extract without any disturbing it. Centrifuge off The crude Tulsi leaf at centrifuge machine, formation of clear solution Collect the pure extract into the sample bottles and this extract is used for the preparation of metallic Nano-particles.

2.3. Dry leaves and their powders

Figure 1 Dry leaves and their powder

2.4. General method of green synthesis of metallic nano-particles

Figure 2 Formation of metallic nanoparticles

Taking 45 ml of leaf extract (Tulsi, Turmeric, Bael and Castor) and add 5 ml of 0.5 M metal solution (NaNO_3 , KNO_3 , $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$) with constant stirring in a Conical flask or beaker. Heat the mixture on a magnetic stirrer at 70-80°C for 40 min. After 30-40 minutes solution colour was changed as shown in fig.no.2 and we concluded that metallic nanoparticles were formed.

2.5. Characterisation techniques of synthesized metallic nanoparticles

The formation of metallic nanoparticles was evaluated by visual assessment of the colour changes of the solutions. The reduction of metallic Nano particle was measured periodically at a wavelength range between 185–800 nm using an ultraviolet-visible (UV-2600 Type Series) spectrophotometer.

The DLS and zeta potential techniques were used to estimate the average particle size and the potential stability of the metallic nanoparticles formed in the solution [15]. The DLS indicates of synthesized various metallic nanoparticles are illustrated in Graph-2. The shape and morphology of the nanoparticles were determined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) [16-17]. This is shown in figure 5. And the synthesized metallic nanoparticle shows antibacterial activity against bacteria E-coli by agar well diffusion method as shown in figure 6.

3. Results and Discussions

The uses of environmentally eco-friendly sustainable solvent water systems and metals are reduced in to their elemental state are observed the most important criteria for green chemistry approach for the synthesis of metallic nanoparticles [8].

3.1. UV-Visible Study

The formation of light to dark brown or pale yellow color of various metallic nanoparticles shows which are an indicative of the reduction of metal ions ($\text{M}^+ \text{ to } \text{M}^0$ where, $\text{M} = \text{Na, K \& Ca}$) in elemental form and were examined by maximum absorption peak observed range between 185 and 800 nm which indicating the crystalline nature. (Graph-1) (1 second time intervals & light source change wavelength at 323nm) at room temperature [9-12].

Many researchers were investigating the change of the optical properties of colloidal solution of metallic nanoparticles and they found Light irradiation reduction of metals, when the various metallic solutions were changed which can be related to the shape and size of the reduced different metallic nanoparticles [13]. For the higher absorption depends upon the change in particle size [14-16].

3.2. DLS study

DLS is the study of the Dynamic light scattering (DLS) technique in which the study of the potential stability of metallic nanoparticles and the average particle size formed in different metallic nanoparticles solution [17-18]. The DLS has been estimating of synthesized metals nanoparticles for various metals and leaves extract nanoparticles in liquid phase are illustrated in Graph-2. So, this is also called as photo correlation spectroscopy [19]. The zeta potential of nanoparticles implies the valuable principal key of stability of metallic nanoparticles and surface charge present on it. Large magnitude of zeta potential designate and high electrical charge on the surface of the nanoparticles can cause strong repulsive force among particles to form clusters. [20]. In the other words by using DLS techniques were emphasized the negative magnitude of zeta potential of metallic nanoparticles ($\xi = -5.16 \text{ to } -20.5 \text{ mV}$) showing longer time stability of these metallic nanoparticles solution. Solution indicating the dissemination of metallic nanoparticles because, off their presents between the negative-negative repulsive forces in the metallic nanoparticles solution.

3.3. SEM Study

The morphology of metallic nanoparticles had studied by SEM. In the present work only study some of the metallic nanoparticles (Tulsi, Turmeric, Bael and Castor of NaNO_3) showing different shapes. The shapes of metallic nanoparticles depends on concentration of plant extract, part of the plant used, rate of mixing metal ions solution and plant extract, time required for reaction and temperature etc. [21]. The reduction of metal ions to fabricate metals nanoparticles by using tea extract, reducing agent and stabilizer, led to the formation of spherical metallic nanoparticles [22-23]. SEM images of various metallic nanoparticles as showing [24-28]. in figure 5

Figure 3 UV Spectra

Figure 4 Dynamic light scattering (DLS)

A

B

C

D

Figure 5 SEM

3.4. Antibacterial activity

We have reported here in vitro screening of wide range of metallic nanoparticles. They were screening of Gram-negative bacteria [29-33]. (E.coli NCIM 2065) and it's compared with ciprofloxacin. The synthesis metallic nanoparticle showed antibacterial activity of E-coli bacteria by agar well diffusion method [34-37]. From the following results of some alkali and alkaline earth metallic nanoparticles has enhanced the better potency of antibacterial activity of E-coli bacteria as showed in table no-1.

Table 1 Antibacterial activities of synthesized metallic nanoparticles

Sr.No.	Name of the Synthesized metallic nanoparticles	Zone of inhibition after 24 hours of incubation in (mm)
1.	Tulsi + KNO ₃	22
2.	Tulsi + NaNO ₃	21
3.	Tulsi + Ca(NO ₃) ₂	21
4.	Turmeric + KNO ₃	25
5.	Turmeric + NaNO ₃	22
6.	Turmeric + Ca(NO ₃) ₂	24
7.	Bael + KNO ₃	19
8.	Bael + NaNO ₃	20
9.	Bael + Ca(NO ₃) ₂	23
10.	Castor + KNO ₃	16
11.	Castor + NaNO ₃	14
12.	Castor + Ca(NO ₃) ₂	15

Figure 6 Antibacterial activities of synthesized metallic nanoparticles

4. Conclusion

The preparation of metallic nanoparticles from the different leaf extract in minimum time, low cost and also simple way. Only water is used as green solvent and its required minimum time to formation of nanoparticles. Also the prepared nanoparticle it exhibit good antibacterial activity. The metallic nanoparticle syntheses by plant extract are characterized by synthesized nanoparticles using uv-visible spectra, PSA, Zeta potential and SEM. The maximum absorbance of metallic nanoparticle by uv-visible spectra was found to be 185 and 800 nm and surface charge determine by Zeta potential. The synthesis metallic nanoparticle shows antibacterial activity against bacteria E-coli by agar well diffusion method. The synthesized Metallic nanoparticles are found to be more susceptible towards the bacterial strains.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors agree no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Kaushik N, Thakkar MS, Snehit S, Mhatre MS, Rasesh Y, Parikh MS, Biological synthesis of metallic nanoparticles Nanomed Nanotechnol Biol Med. (2010);6:257–262.
- [2] Kubik B, Sugisaka M, molecular biology to nanotechnology and nanomedicine. Biosystems (2002); 65:123–138
- [3] Lateef A, Ojo SA, Elegbede JA, the emerging roles of arthropods and their metabolites in the green synthesis of metallic nanoparticles. Nanotechnol Rev. (2016); 5:601–622
- [4] Duan H, Wang D, Li Y, Green chemistry for nanoparticle synthesis. Chem Soc Rev (2015); 44:5778–5792
- [5] Imtiyaz Hussain. N. B. Singh, Ajey Singh, Himani Singh, S. C. Singh, Green synthesis of nanoparticles and its potential Application Biotechnol Lett. (2016); 38:545–560.
- [6] Sapana Jadoun, Rizwan Arif, Nirmala Kumari Jangid, Rajesh Kumar Meen Green synthesis of nanoparticles using plant extracts: a review- Environmental Chemistry Letter (2021); 355-374.
- [7] Adam S, Gabriela K, Ivo S, Mirka S and et al., Applications of biosynthesized metallic nanoparticles – A review, Acta Biomaterialia (2014); 10: 4023–4042.
- [8] N. Asfaw, Y. Chebude, A. Ejigu, R.B. Hurisso, P. Licence, R.L. Smith, S.L.Y. Tangb, M. Poliakoff, The 13 principles of green chemistry and engineering for a greener Africa Green Chemistry(2011);13: 1059–1060.

- [9] Gloria Aderonke Otunola and Anthony Jide Afolayan, In vitro antibacterial, antioxidant and toxicity profile of silver nanoparticles green-synthesized and characterized from aqueous extract of a spice blend formulation, *Biotechnology & Biotechnological Equipment* (2018); (<https://doi.org/10.1080/13102818.2018.1448301>)
- [10] Raza MA, Kanwal Z, Rauf A, et al., Size- and shape-dependent antibacterial studies of silver nanoparticles synthesized by wet chemical routes. *Nanomaterial* (2016); (DOI: 10.3390/nano6040074).
- [11] Abdhul Basheer Chanthini, Govindasamy Balasubramani, et al, Structural characterization, antioxidant and in vitro cytotoxic properties of seagrass, *Cymodocea serrulata* (R.Br.) Asch. & Magnus mediated Silver nanoparticles, *Journal of Photochemistry & Photobiology, B: Biology* (2015); 153:145–152.
- [12] Mohammad Ovesa, Mohammad Aslama, Mohd Ahmar Rauf b, Shariq Qayyumb, et. al, Antimicrobial and anticancer activities of silver nanoparticles synthesized from the root hair extract of *Phoenix dactylifera* *Materials Science & Engineering C*: (2018); 89:429–443.
- [13] Quang H T, Van Q Nand Anh-Tuan L, Silver nanoparticles: synthesis, properties, toxicology, applications and perspectives. *Adv. Nat. Sci.: Nano-sci. Nanotechnol* (2013); 4 033001.
- [14] Rao YN, Banerjee D, Datta A, Das SK, Guin R and Saha A, Gamma irradiation route to synthesis of highly re-dispersible natural polymer capped silver nanoparticles *Radiat. Phys.Chem.*(2010); 79: 1240–6.
- [15] Sujata Patra ,Sudip Mukherjee , Ayan Kumar Barui, Anirban Ganguly, et.al., Green synthesis, characterization of gold and silver nanoparticles and their potential application for cancer therapeutics. *Materials Science and Engineering C*:(2015); 53: 298–309.
- [16] Baharara J, Namvar F, Ramezani T, Mousavi M, Mohamad R., Silver nanoparticles biosynthesized using *Achillea biebersteinii* flower extract: apoptosis induction in MCF-7 cells via caspase activation and regulation of Bax and Bcl-2 gene expression. *Molecules*: (2015); 20(2):2693–2706.
- [17] Mata R, Nakkala JR, Sadras SR., Catalytic and biological activities of green silver nanoparticles synthesized from *Plumeria Alba* (frangipani) flower extract. *Mater.Sci. Eng. C. Mater. Biol. Appl.*(2015); 51: 216–225.
- [18] Vijayaraghavan K, Nalini SK, Prakash NU, Madhankumar D. one step green synthesis of silver nano/microparticles using extracts of *Trachyspermum ammi* and *Papaver somniferum*. *Colloids and Surfaces B: Bio interfaces* (2012); 94: 114-117.(<http://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfb.2012.01.026>)
- [19] Shakil A, Nilofar Y, Md. Atikur, Abdullah Md., Green synthesis of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs): Agricultural applications and future vision. *J. Bio. Env. Sci.* (2018); Vol. 13, No. 2: 35-57.
- [20] Pantelis K, Andreas D, VassilsZ, Dimitriosp, Sofia A T, NikolaosM, Green synthesis and characterization of silver nanoparticles produced using *Arbutus Unedo* leaf extract, *Materials Letters* (2012) ;76:18-20
- [21] Yugang Sun and Younan Xia, Shape controlled synthesis of gold and silver nanoparticles, *Science* (2002); 298:2176-2179.
- [22] Yun Fang, Ci-Qing Hong, Fang-Rong Chen, Fang-Ze Gui, et.al. Green synthesis of nano silver by tea extract with high antimicrobial activity. *Inorganic Chemistry Communications* (2021); 132:108808.
- [23] Shiv Shankar, Absar Ahmad and Murali Shastry, Geranium leaf assisted biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles, *Biotechnol prog.* (2009);19: 1627-1631.
- [24] Gurunathan s., Han J.W., Dayem A.A., Eppakayala V., Park J.H., et.al, Green synthesis of anisotropic silver nanoparticles and its potential cytotoxicity in human breast cancer cells (MCF-7), *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.* (2013);19: 1600–1605.
- [25] Chitra G., Balasubramani G., Ramkumar R., Sowmiya R., Perumal P.,*Mukia maderaspatana* (Cucurbitaceae) extract-mediated synthesis of silver nanoparticles to control *Culex quinquefasciatus* and *Aedes aegypti* (Diptera: Culicidae), *Parasitol.Res.* (2015); 114: 1407–1415.
- [26] Fenglin H., Ruili L., Bao H., Liang M., Free radical scavenging activity of extracts prepared from fresh leaves of selected Chinese medicinal plants, *Fitoterapia* (2004); 75:14–23.
- [27] Bhatt K.D, Deshmukh K.M, Patil Y.P. Synthesis of powdered silver nanoparticles using hydrogen in aqueous Medium. *Particuology* (2012) ; 10(1), 140–143.
- [28] Rai M, Kon K, Ingle A, Duran N, Galdiero S, Galdiero M. Broad-spectrum bioactivities of silver nanoparticles: the emerging trends and future prospects. *Appl. Microbial. Biotechnol.* (2014); 98(5), 1951–1961.

- [29] Singh P, Kim YJ, Singh H et al. Biosynthesis characterization, and antimicrobial applications of silver nanoparticles. *Int. J. Nanomedicine* (2015); 10, 2567.
- [30] Mukherjee S, Dasari M, Priyamvada S, Kotcherlakota R, Bollu VS, Patra CR. A green chemistry approach for the synthesis of gold nanoconjugates that induce the inhibition of cancer cell proliferation through induction of oxidative stress and their in vivo toxicity study. *J. Mater. Chem. B.* (2015); 3(18): 3820–3830.
- [31] Mittal AK, Chisti Y, Banerjee UC., Synthesis of metallic nanoparticles using plant extracts. *Biotechnol. Adv.* (2013); 31(2): 346–356.
- [32] Veerasamy R, Xin TZ, Gunasagaran S et al., Biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles using mangosteen leaf extract and evaluation of their antimicrobial activities. *J. Saudi Chem. Soc.* (2011); 15(2):113–120.
- [33] Iravani S, Zolfaghari B., Green synthesis of silver nanoparticles using *Pinus eldarica* bark extract. *Biomed Res.Int.* (2013); 639725.
- [34] Zhang Y, Cheng X, Zhang Y, Xue X, Fu Y., A Biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles at room temperature using aqueous aloe leaf extract and antibacterial properties. *Colloids Surf.* (2013); A 423:63–68. (2013).
- [35] Mukherjee P, Ahmad A, Mandal D, Senapati S, Sainkar S.R., et al. Fungus-mediated synthesis of silver nanoparticles and their immobilization in the mycelial matrix: a novel biological approach to nanoparticle synthesis. *Nano Lett.* (2011); 1:515–519.
- [36] Sharma V. K., Yngard R. A., Lin Y. *Adv. Silver nanoparticles: green synthesis and their antimicrobial activities.* *Colloid Interface Sci.* (2009); 145:83–96.
- [37] Nadagouda M. N, Varma R. S, Synthesis of thermally stable carboxymethyl cellulose or metal biodegradable nanocomposite films for potential biological applications. *Biomacromolecules* (2007) ; 8: 2762–2767.